

Multiple comparison procedures renewed.
An overview of the Dunnett's test and its application:
using CRAN R packages

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Abstract

This essay presents the Dunnett test for comparing a control with multiple treatment groups and its modifications from five principles: i) formulated as a multiple contrast test, ii) modified using multiple marginal models (mmm), iii) the availability of interpretable simultaneous confidence intervals (beyond p-values), iv) realization in CRAN packages and v) illustration using data examples. This also results in limitations, e.g., the concise presentation of stepwise procedures. The main purpose is to show how versatile the Dunnett test can be applied to a wide range of data conditions, models and designs - and to do so relatively easily.

1 Starting position

Dunnett's test is so widespread used because simultaneous comparisons of several treatments against a negative control (or untreated condition, or placebo in randomized clinical trials) for superiority in a randomized one-way layout are rather typical in biomedicine. A lot is available on modifications of the Dunnett test, more than you might think at first sight. This essay gives an overview and focuses particularly on the realization with CRAN packages, demonstrating by real data examples.

2 The original publication Dunnett (1955) [28]

Starting point are one- and two-sided simultaneous confidence intervals for $(\mu_i - \mu_0)$ as improvement of the early procedure according to Roessler [108] in the forties, who assumed independence between the comparisons using the Bonferroni adjustment. Dunnett's paper based on the generalization of the two-sample t-statistics to several comparisons versus control and their common multivariate t-distribution (with explicit representation of the correlation) according to the fundamental previous work on the bivariate, correlated t-distribution [29]. Common for that time, some quantile tables are given and a chapter on the optimal design n_0/n_i completes the original approach.

Numerous generalizations of the original 1955 approach have been published in the seventies by [119] (as multiple contrast) up to now [53] (most likely transformation version). The objective here is not to discuss alternatives with power advantages, but rather generalizations, e.g. in generalized linear (mixed) model glmm and further robust modifications, e.g. for variance heterogeneity.

3 Dunnett's procedure formulated as multiple contrast test

As a generalization of Dunnett's procedure, already in the seventies Shaffer [119] introduced the multiple contrast approach. In the concept of multiple contrast tests [92], the single contrast is defined as a suitable linear combination of estimators $\sum_{i=0}^k c_i \bar{y}_i$ where the expected value μ_i is used as the effect size here as dominating in literature. Other effect sizes, such as risk difference, risk ratio, odds ratio, hazard ratio or relative effect size can be used (see below)- an essential advantage of this approach. Here $i = 0, \dots, k$, focusing on comparisons vs. control only in a possibly unbalanced one-way layout for a single primary endpoint y_{ij} , a single qualitative factor f , where the error term is assumed to be normally distributed with homogeneous variances: $y_{ij} = \mu + f_i + \epsilon_{ij}$. A contrast test is the standardized (ie. studentized) version:

$t_{Contrast} = \sum_{i=0}^k c_i \bar{y}_i / S \sqrt{\sum_i c_i^2 / n_i}$ where c_i^q are the contrast coefficients. The condition $\sum_{i=0}^k c_i = 0$ guarantees a $t_{df, 1-\alpha}$ distributed level- α -test. To achieve compatible simultaneous confidence intervals the further condition must hold $\sum sign^+(c_i) = 1, \sum sign^-(c_i) = 1$. Notice, arbitrary c_i can be used in resampling tests- *may be a reason for their popularity*. A multiple contrast test is defined as maxT test: $t_{MCT} = max(t_1, \dots, t_q)$ (where the number and kind of included tests q is discussed below) which follows jointly a $(t_1, \dots, t_q)'$ a q -variate t -distribution with the common degree of freedom df and correlation matrix R ($R = f(c_{ij}, n_i)$). This approach based on a common variance estimator S and common df in the $k + 1$ one-way layout. Notice, R can be more complicated, e.g. when variance heterogeneity is considered or a ratio-to-control estimator is used, see below). The R-library (*mvtnorm*) is available for random, density, quantile or probability (r,d,q,p-) of the (non)-central multivariate t-distribution for any correlation matrix [90, 13]. The common-used adjusted p-values are given by $\frac{\sum_{i=0}^k c_i \bar{y}_i}{S \sqrt{\sum_i c_i^2 / n_i}} = t_{q, df, R, 1-sided, 1-min(\alpha)}$. Compatible to the adjusted p-

values are two- or one-sided (here lower) simultaneous confidence limits: $[\sum_{i=0}^k c_i \bar{y}_i - S \cdot t_{q, df, R, 1-sided, 1-\alpha} \sqrt{\sum_i c_i^2 / n_i}]$. The choice of a particular contrast matrix defines the particular MCT. Here, well-known examples for the simple balanced design ($k = 2 + 1$) are:

c_i	C	T_1	T_2
c_a	-1	0	1
c_b	-1	1	0

Table 1:
Dunnett
(one-sided)
[28]

c_i	C	T_1	T_2
c_a	-1	0	1
c_b	-1	1	0
c_c	0	-1	1
c_d	1	-1	0
c_e	-1	1	0
c_f	0	1	-1

Table 2:
All pairs
comparisons
(Tukey1953)

c_i	C	D_1	D_2
c_a	-1	0	1
c_b	-1	1/2	1/2

Table 3:
Williams
(one-sided)
[12]

If one compares this with other contrast matrices, e.g. for change point and grand mean comparisons, the question arises, which and how many individual contrasts should be chosen. A general solution does not seem to exist and different requirements are contradictory. There should be as few contrasts as possible (to limit conservatism), but as

many to characterize all possible aspects of the specific alternatives of interest. They should also be as highly correlated as possible, otherwise their content is too diverse to characterize all possible features of the specific alternative. If the approach of contrasts is extended to linear models (using mmm, see below), this relationship becomes even more complex.

c_i	C	D_1	D_2
c_a	-1	0.5	0.5
c_b	-0.5	-0.5	1

Table 4:
Change-point
comparisons
[46]

c_i	C	D_1	D_2
c_a	-1	1/2	1/2
c_b	1/2	-1	1/2
c_c	1/2	1/2	-1

Table 5:
Grand Mean
comparisons
[100]

3.1 Properties of the maxT test

The Dunnett test is a maxT test, where the maxT test is an union-intersection test (UIT). This test was introduced by Tippett in the thirties [123] as min-p-test (which is under some conditions the same). Currently, the min-p test is popular, especially in the field of quantitative genetics [34]. The maxT test is considered here as a global test in one-way layout. The maxT-test is univariate skewed-t distributed, which is expressed by k-variate distribution $t_{k,df,R,1-\alpha}$, e.g. by library (*mvtnorm*). Fundamental to achieve individual inference, i.e. adjusted p-values or simultaneous confidence intervals, for single step procedures is Gabriel's monotonicity theorem for UIT's [31](abbrev.):

$$t_{k,df,R,1-\alpha} < t_{k-1,df,R,1-\alpha} < \dots < t_{k=1,df,R,1-\alpha} = t_{df,1-\alpha}.$$

Since this is much more complex for stepwise procedures (such as Holm's step-down or Hochberg's step-up), the lifelong consequence for me was not to focus on modifications of stepwise procedures. Their power gains are usually small compared to the restriction of the alternative or the appropriate consideration of the correlations in single step procedures.

3.1.1 Diagnostic properties of maxT test

Years ago [19] discussed the diagnostic properties of maxT test from several perspectives: i) linear combinations of t_q could increase the power, but at the expense of the diagnostic accuracy, ii) the different t_q should describe different aspects of the alternative (where non-nested hypotheses are considered here), iii) the allowance for selection based on Gabriel's monotonicity theorem, iv) the contradiction that with increasing k the power decreases (especially when comparing with quadratic tests), the diagnostic interpretability increases in principle, v) and central: *effective power should be defined to be the probability of detecting a departure from the null hypothesis and of making the correct diagnosis.*

The selection of the best sub-model(s) for the maxT test differs in principle from common model selection methods. These do not know any multiplicity adjustment for several correlated candidate models, but they identify the best model(s) based on a compromise criterion between model fit and sparseness. A possible approach to achieve such model selection properties in the maxT test is a model majority voting of an external bootstrap procedure, shown for change point contrasts [83].

For the time being it remains: to characterize the comparison with p_{min}^{adj} as the 'best' in the maxT test is problematic in terms of model selection. The challenge is to formulate the models in such a way that they are as highly correlated and as little as possible (to limit conservatism), on the other hand to describe as many (but not 'all') aspects of the alternative as possible - usually a fundamental contradiction. A definition of Cox's effective goodness is missing. At least there are voices against the max-power postulate in multiple testing [48].

3.1.2 Selected properties of the k-variate t-distribution

A summary of the properties of the multivariate normal and t-distribution is given in the book [33] and with respect of multiple tests in the thesis of Hasler [36]. A good overview on the related functionality in R can be found in the CRAN Task View 'Probability Distributions, Continuous multivariate distributions' (<https://cran.r-project.org/web/views/Distributions.html>). A short overview:

Correlated tests: $t_{k,df,\mathbb{R},1-\alpha} \xrightarrow{\mathbb{R} \Rightarrow 1} t_{df,1-\alpha}$

Uncorrelated tests: $t_{k,df,\mathbb{R},1-\alpha} \xrightarrow{\mathbb{R} \Rightarrow 0} t_{df,1-\alpha}/k$

Asymptotic tests: $t_{k,df,\mathbb{R},1-\alpha} \xrightarrow{n_i \Rightarrow \infty} z_{k,\mathbb{R},1-\alpha}$

Monotonicity property: $t_{k,df,\mathbb{R},1-\alpha} > t_{k-1,df,\mathbb{R},1-\alpha} > \dots > t_{k=1,df,\mathbb{R},1-\alpha} = t_{df,1-\alpha}$

Symmetry property: $t_{k,df,\mathbb{R},1-\alpha} = -t_{k,df,\mathbb{R},\alpha}$

UIT: maxT test: $maxT > t_{k,df,\mathbb{R},1-\alpha}$

3.1.3 The five different ways to present the joint distribution of a maxT test

Currently there seem to be five options to present the joint distribution of a maxT test: i) Bonferroni, ii) $t_{k,df,R,1-\alpha}$ distribution, iii) multiple marginal models (mmm) [106], iv) permutation tests, and v) copula approach [96, 97]. This essay focuses mainly on ii) and iii). The Bonferroni approach $\alpha_i = \alpha/k$ is the most simple one and rather general, but quite conservative because ignoring the correlations. Regardless of this, it should always be considered as a benchmark, especially in simulations. Using $t_{k,df,R,1-\alpha}$ distribution (ii) represents the standard in simultaneous inference, where the correlation matrix must be formulated explicitly, e.g. using library (*multcomp*) [66]. The correlation matrix in mmm (iii) is estimated from multiple glmm-models directly, ie. must not be formulated and allows models instead of just contrast tests. Thus it is the most general approach, which is presented in several chapters. Permutation tests are widely used, particularly in high dimension problems. Nevertheless, these are hardly discussed here, since with the assumed low dimension they do not show advantages over ii). Copula approaches (v) can overcome the paradigm of the projection method into rectangular intervals. This new approach will certainly be further developed soon.

3.1.4 The central condition of the *glht()* function in library(*multcomp*)

The central part of the library *multcomp* is the function *glht()*. Via object-oriented programming it based on the coefficients (*coef()*) and variance-covariance matrix *vcov()* of linear, generalized linear and generalized linear mixed effect models. By mean of the function *linfct()* the particular linear hypotheses for differences are specified, either for any linear model function or particularly multiple comparisons using the argument *mcp()*. Here central is the function *contrMat()* (or symbolic statements such as 'Dunnett') where the type of MCP are defined. Moreover, the argument *rhs()* allows even non-null shifted hypotheses. For the above defined conditions, the function *glht()* exact the particular multivariate t distribution and provides adjusted p-values or simultaneous confidence interval for differences [64].

3.1.5 Further maxT test applications

The MCP-mod approach use the maxT test as an option (as alternative to AIC) in model selection [105] (see the relation *selModel="Tmax"* option the in the CRAN package *DoseFinding*). For comparing curves in the CRAN package *curvecomp* the *option="MaxT"* is in the function *param.boot* available. Nonparametric association between two random vectors of arbitrary dimensions decomposed in all atomic partitions and combined by Fisher or minP [17] (in the function *fast.independence.test* are available in the CRAN package *HHG*). Pointwise maxT of functional data were described [125] and multiple categorization schemes, multiple Box-Cox transformations or multiple fractional polynomial transformations for a continuous covariate [87] as well as maximally selected rank statistics, i.e., maximum over all possible dichotomisations of continuous variable [67, 66] are available.

3.2 Multiple marginal models

The multiple marginal models (mmm) approach [106] based on maxT tests and provides the joint distribution of parameter estimates from multiple generalized linear (mixed) linear models. This is a substantial advantage over the multiple contrast tests approach, where the correlation matrix R must be calculated from the design for rather limited configurations. Analogously, adjusted p-values or simultaneous confidence intervals are available, however without the need of explicit formulation of the correlation matrix. In the function *mmm()*, the variance-covariance matrix of parameter estimates can be maintained using derivatives of the log-likelihood function in a single model, and therefore a vector of log-likelihood functions is used for multiple models. This vector-valued asymptotic representation is based on standardized score vectors as the sum of i.i.d. normally distributed random variables. Plugging in parameter estimates yields a consistent sandwich estimator of the variance-covariance matrix, i.e., the empirical covariance based on functions of the data rather than the data themselves. Three features are required: i) the problem-relevant formulated maxT test, ii) the multiple marginal models from the class of lm, lmm (with constraints), glm, or glmm (with constraints), and iii) a unique data matrix for all marginal models (what to consider in case of missings or pseudo-missings). The basic function *mmm* is available within the R package *multcomp* [66] and the function *lmer2lm* for transformation glmm's into lm's [115], [72]. The diversity of applications of the mmm method is impressive, see details in [63].

3.3 The concept of familywise error rate

The FWER concept is not too obvious, i.e. what is the family in practice when we consider not only between treatment levels comparisons? There are two extremes: first the global FWER concept, i.e. a certain α -level is controlled for all occurring sources of multiplicity, e.g. between treatment (or dose) levels, ii) between times, iii) between endpoints, iv) between stages in adaptive designs, v) between test statistics, vi) between subgroups, vii) between several effect sizes, viii) between different modeling styles, e.g. dose considered as factor or as covariate. This can be easily performed by

Bonferroni-approach, which results in a rather conservative procedure (ignoring correlations). Maybe not too bad (remember genome-wise associations studies with 10^{-6} [118] fix threshold) A second approach is CWER (per-comparisons wise error rate): each test at level α . Don't smile: reality!. There are two compromises: i) per method-control (using Dunnett test between T_i , ignoring the rest). ii) **claimwise error rate** [104], i.e. the family is defined via the intended claims.

3.4 One-sided and two-sided hypotheses- directional errors

One advantage of the Dunnett procedure is the ease with which one-sided or two-sided hypotheses can be formulated, and hence corresponding p-values and confidence limits. Surprisingly, in practice these two-sided tests dominate, although in most experiments the beneficial direction of the primary endpoint is known. It is curious that this considerable loss of power is accepted - after all, these are uncorrelated tests for increase and decrease, each at the $\alpha/2$ level. Later, attempts are sometimes made to generate a usually much smaller power advantage by complex stepwise procedures. Of course, directional errors (type III) are devastating, but hardly ever occur with careful analysis [128]. Two-sided testing based on the contrast matrix for both increase and decrease:

c_i	C	T_1	T_2
c_a	-1	0	1
c_b	-1	1	0
c_c	1	-1	0
c_d	1	0	-1

Table 6: Two-sided Dunnett type comparisons

Of course, the two-sided 95% multi-t quantile is identical to the one-sided 97.5% quantile (note the limited precision of the approximate approach in `library(mvtnorm)`).

Contrast	C	T_1	T_2
c_a	-1	0	1
c_b	-1	1	0
c_c	1	-1	0
c_d	1	0	-1

Table 7: Two-sided Dunnett type comparisons

3.5 Adjusted p-values, simultaneous confidence intervals and their compatibility

Initially, the Dunnett MCT is a global test. Based on Gabriel's monotonicity theorem a single step procedure (see above) allows the local decisions of interest, i.e. adjusted p-values and simultaneous confidence intervals (sCI). Because by means of sCI the clinically relevant effect size and its uncertainty are directly interpretable, sCI clearly represent the means of choice. Whenever adjusted p-values and sCI should be compatible, i.e., lead to the same decisions H_0/H_1 . This is obvious for normal distribution, but not at all, e.g. using small n_i approximations for the difference of proportions. This important aspect is illustrated by two examples. First, the pub weights in a toxicological bioassay with 3 doses and a control and two covariates (gestation time and litter size) [127] are considered. The Dunnett-type adjusted p-values and the simultaneous confidence limits, one-sided for a decrease (which is of toxicological relevance) are compatible assuming normal distributed homoscedastic errors, yielding to the same decisions for the 3 contrasts:

Comparison	adjusted p-value	Decision test	Upper 95% confidence limit	Decision sCI
5-0	0.016	significant decrease	-0.63	significant decrease
50-0	0.112	no decision against H_0	0.54	no decision against H_0
500-0	0.063	no decision against H_0	0.14	no decision against H_0

Table 8: Compatible p-value and confidence limit

Non-compatibility is illustrated by means of a second example, where proportions of patients with marked improvement of psoriasis were considered in a placebo controlled clinical trial with three dose groups of the drug liarozole [8]. The Dunnett-type two-sided 95% confidence limits were estimated for the differences of proportions in the standard glm, whereas the adjusted p-value were estimated by the ADD2-small sample modification [113] using the library (`MCPAN`):

Further, the use of compatibility intervals is recommended, i.e. sCI with problem-appropriate effect size, sCI which fit the data conditions, sCI using coverage levels which are appropriate to the research question [53].

Comparison	p-value	Decision test	Lower 95% confidence limit	Decision CI
50-Placebo	0.19	no decision against H_0	-0.29	no decision against H_0
75-Placebo	0.51	no decision against H_0	-0.19	no decision against H_0
150-Placebo	0.002	significant increase	-0.51	no decision against H_0

Table 9: Non-compatible p-value and confidence limit for the difference of proportions

4 Modification for heteroscedasticity in the general unbalanced design

One of the basic assumptions of the Dunnett test (besides normally distributed errors) is homoscedasticity because using the common (i.e., for all $k+1$ groups), MQR estimator and the common df. But, variance heterogeneity is sometimes present in real data, random or structural (e.g., increasing variance with increasing effect). Especially in unbalanced designs, the false positive rate is then modified: i) conservative if $s_i \gg s_0; n_i < n_0$, ii) but even level violating liberal if $s_0 \gg s_i; n_0 < n_i$. But also power is influenced. Two different modifications of the original test are available: i) use of the sandwich variance estimator [45], ii) use of reduced df [39, 37]. Both procedures are effective (with i) requiring more asymptotic conditions [38]). To demonstrate a possible bias by other groups with higher variance a simulated dose-response data example is used. Here is usually used a design where the medium and high dose are effective, the low not. However, if the low dose has a high variance, this can bias the detection of the medium dose in particular.

Figure 1: Simulated dose-response data

The standard Dunnett test is compared with both modified approaches in comparison to Bonferroni-adjusted Welch-t-tests:

```
library(SimComp); set.seed(127711)
D3<- ermvnorm(n=9,mean=14, sd=1.25)
D2 <- ermvnorm(n=10 ,mean=11.25, sd=1.35)
D1 <- ermvnorm(n=6 ,mean=10.5, sd=6.5)
Control <- ermvnorm(n=16 ,mean=10, sd=1.2)
dose <- factor(rep(c("Control","D1","D2", "D3"), c(16,6,10,9)))
Response <- c(Control, D1, D2, D3)
datBias <- data.frame(Response, dose)

library(multcomp); library(sandwich); library(SimComp); library(pairwiseCI)
mod1<-lm(Response~dose, data=datBias)
hom<-summary(glht(mod1, linfct = mcp(dose = "Dunnett"),alternative="greater"))
sand<-summary(glht(mod1, linfct = mcp(dose = "Dunnett"), alternative="greater",vcov=vcovHC))
has1<-summary(SimTestDiff(data=datBias, grp="dose", resp="Response", type="Dunnett",
                          alternative="greater", covar.equal=FALSE))
scaa <- summary(pairwiseTest(Response ~ dose, data=datBias, method="t.test",
                              var.equal=FALSE, alternative="greater", control="Control"),
                p.adjust.method="bonferroni")
```

The standard test does not detect the medium dose (D2) as increased versus control both modified approaches and the Bonferroni-Welch-test approach do.

5 Ratio-to-control inference

Although the difference is used dominantly as effect size for Dunnett tests in the literature, ratios-to-control as effect size in the multiplicative model show advantages, e.g. the dimensionless effect size of the easy to interpret percent change, but also disadvantages, e.g. the instability at $\mu_0 \Rightarrow 0$. For normal distributed and homoscedastic errors, related simultaneous Fieller-type lower confidence limits based on the contrast test $T_i^{Ratio} = \frac{\bar{X}_i - \theta \bar{X}_0}{S \sqrt{\frac{1}{n_i} + \frac{\theta^2}{n_0}}}$ for the hypotheses: $H_{0i} : \frac{\mu_i}{\mu_0} \leq \theta$ vs. $H_{1i} : \frac{\mu_i}{\mu_0} > \theta$ [21]:

$$\hat{\theta}_{lower}^{(l)} = \frac{-V_i - \sqrt{V_i^2 - 4U_i W_i}}{2U_i}$$

$$\begin{aligned} U_i &= \left(\sum_{i=0}^k d_{li} \bar{X}_i \right)^2 - t_{k,1-\alpha}^2(df, \hat{\mathbf{R}}) S^2 \sum_{i=0}^k d_{li}^2 / n_i, \\ V_i &= -2 \left(\left(\sum_{i=0}^k c_{li} \bar{X}_i \right) \left(\sum_{i=0}^k d_{li} \bar{X}_i \right) - t_{k,1-\alpha}^2(df, \hat{\mathbf{R}}) S^2 \sum_{i=0}^k c_{li} d_{li} / n_i \right), \\ W_i &= \left(\sum_{i=0}^k c_{li} \bar{X}_i \right)^2 - t_{k,1-\alpha}^2(df, \hat{\mathbf{R}}) S^2 \sum_{i=0}^k c_{li}^2 / n_i \end{aligned}$$

where c_{li} and d_{li} are the contrast coefficient in nominator and denominator. The elements of the correlation matrix $\hat{\mathbf{R}}$ are rather complex because they depend not only on c_{li} and d_{li} but also on the unknown ratios θ_{i0} (plugged-in approach) [21]. The related functions for adjusted p-values or simultaneous confidence intervals are available in the CRAN package *mratios* [22]. The comparison between confidence intervals for the difference-to-control and ratio-to-control is illustrated by the cholesterol data example (available in library(*multcomp*)- without considering drugE):

Both intervals show the same qualitative decision. A remarkable difference lies in the interpretation of the lower limit relevant here (for 1 times) -13.1 response vs. 20.9%. The package *mratios* contains the function *gsci.ratio()* which allows the evaluation of mixed effect models as well. Here, the heart rate example from library(*asbio*) is used. From the object of the fitted mixed effect model `mixmod <- lme(rate ~ drug-1, data=heart, random=~1 .. time)` the ML-estimates `estm` and the variance-covariance matrix `vcm` are used in `gsci.ratio` together with the contrast matrix for nominator and denominator `gsci.ratio(estm, vcm, Num.Contrast=CMR$numC, Den.Contrast=CMR$denC)` (details, see the Appendix in chapter 20.6).

Figure 2: Cholesterol example: confidence intervals for the difference-to-control and ratio-to-control

6 Closed testing procedure for treatments vs. control comparisons

The closed testing procedure (CTP) [89] and the maxT test use almost contrary principles for the same objective. While the maxT test tests each elementary hypothesis to an adjusted α -level (e.g. α/q)-based on the union-intersection (UIT) principle (*'or, ..., or'*), in the CTP each elementary hypothesis is tested to the full α -level, but not alone, rather within an intersection-union (IUT) principle (*'and, ..., and'*), where all hypotheses in the intersection branch of the closed system tree must also be under H_1 (each at α -level). The maxT test requires a complex multivariate t-distribution and their correlation matrix, whereas the CTP requires only an univariate (F, or t-) distribution (without considering correlation).

Central to the CTP is the definition of the elementary hypotheses, which alone are of interest and are then to be interpreted. Right here $H_i : \mu_i - \mu_0$. Based on this all subset intersection hypotheses up to the global hypothesis are constructed, involving H_{i0} . Following from the UIT principle, H_i is rejected at level α if and only if H_i itself is rejected and all hypotheses which include them. Each of these many hypotheses is tested individually with a level α -test. This may be any appropriate level α -test, making the CPT flexible. Even within a tree, different tests, e.g. F-tests and t-tests, can be used. Each of these branches-tests of the tree (determined by the ξ elementary hypotheses) represent an uncorrelated IUT, i.e. $T^{CTP} = \min(T_1, \dots, T_\xi)$, or $p^{CTP} = \max(p_1, \dots, p_\xi)$. Comparing to the control form a complete family of hypotheses [121] avoiding complex subset intersection hypotheses of the style $H_0^{1,2}, H_0^{3,4}$. For the simple design with $k = 2 + 1$ the family include the elementary, intersection and global hypotheses [65]:

$$\begin{aligned}
 H_0^{01} : \mu_0 = \mu_1 &\subset [H_0^{012}, H_0^{013}] \subset H_0^{0123} \\
 H_0^{02} : \mu_0 = \mu_2 &\subset [H_0^{012}, H_0^{023}] \subset H_0^{0123} \\
 H_0^{03} : \mu_0 = \mu_3 &\subset [H_0^{013}, H_0^{023}] \subset H_0^{0123}
 \end{aligned}$$

The usual CTP-version for treatment comparisons uses F-tests (and thus two-sided hypotheses) in global, partition and elementary hypotheses. Alternatively, global tests can be used for comparisons to the overall mean (CTP-GM) in the global and partition hypotheses (as a max-p test of the corresponding multiple contrast test [100]). This considers only k comparisons and has a similar power as F-tests [77]. In the elementary hypotheses, instead of pairwise t-tests, multiple contrasts for $\mu_i - \mu_0$ are used, which exploit the entire df , a significant power advantage especially for small n_i . Another alternative is to use global Dunnett multiple contrast tests. To avoid directional errors, this makes it easy to formulate CTP for one-sided hypotheses. A power comparison of these three variants with the Dunnett procedure as the gold standard shows, unsurprisingly, that no uniformly powerful test exists

[56]. However, there are power advantages of the GM-CTP for the relevant alternatives $[0, 0, \dots, 0, \delta]$ or $[0, 0, \dots, \delta, \delta]$. Despite difficult availability of simultaneous confidence intervals, the above CTP modifications represent practically-relevant alternatives to the gold standard, especially in terms of ease of generalizability (e.g., in glmm) and extensibility (e.g., for multiple endpoints).

Both CTP and maxT test become more conservative with increasing number of elementary hypotheses. Controlling FWER, this implies an inherent power loss compared to a single test. In the maxT test, this is determined by the number q of individual tests in the q -variate (t) distribution, with the correlation between the tests having a conservatism-reducing effect. In contrast, the conservativeness of the CTP is due to that of the underlying IUT in the branches of the CTP decision tree, disregarding the correlation between the individual tests. Furthermore, the number and type of individual tests in the IUT's depends on the specific structure of the CTP tree (see e.g. chapter). If the number of individual tests is too high within each IUT (and e.g. 10 are quickly reached in real applications), it becomes hopelessly conservative - a limitation of the CTP in principle to low dimensional cases.

7 Evaluation of two-way layouts as example of a factorial design

Often the Dunnett test is used alone for one-way layouts, which are typical for randomized clinical trials (RCT), e.g. the comparison of hazard rate of three treatments arms against reference [3]. In addition, there are factorial designs with additional fixed factors or even with random factors (see below). For the sake of simplicity, a two-way layout is considered here. We assume, the factors have only a few levels and usually a primary factor exists, e.g. dose, which is to be evaluated with respect to comparisons to the control, and furthermore a secondary factor, e.g. gender, which is to be analyzed appropriately. Usually, separate Dunnett tests are performed on the levels of the secondary factor if the global interaction term of the ANOVA F-test is not significant, and a Dunnett test across the pooled levels otherwise. But a pre-test on negligible interaction formulated for an equivalence hypothesis requires the a-priori definition of the still tolerated threshold, which is difficult to practically impossible [20]. Moreover, the interaction term is a global test, which does not recognize different possible local interaction patterns. In addition, error control and power of conditional tests (pre-test, main-test) are difficult in general. Instead of a pre-test approach, a simultaneous single-step procedure, considering of ϑ Dunnett tests jointly, each of the ϑ levels of the secondary factor [64, 60]. Extending this approach, the global Dunnett test and the ϑ secondary level tests are recommended simultaneously, since a problem-adequate interpretation is possible and the inherent loss of power is small in relation [58, 57]. As an example, the baseline adjusted abdominal pain score is considered as primary endpoint in a unbalanced randomized dose finding trial with 4 doses and placebo to treat the irritable bowel syndrome in males and females, as the secondary factor [9].

This example is specific because the interactions F-test is not significant ($p = 0.72$), and therefore, for the most part, only a Dunnett test would be performed across all data. Table 10 shows the one-sided adjusted p-values for the 12 individual comparisons for the joint test considering males, females and pooled data (using sandwich estimator accounting for possible heteroscedasticity [44]). Significant increases for higher doses (2,3,4) vs. placebo in the pooled analysis are remarkable, revealing a higher sensitivity in females compared to males in their simultaneous analysis. The price of conservatism is relatively high in this data example: e.g. the analysis of the pooled data alone yields a p-value of 0.01 for the $[4 - 0]$ comparison compared with 0.026 in the joint test here.

Of course, the interpretability of the joint test depends on only a few levels of the primary factor, and especially on only a few levels of the secondary factor, with a total of about two secondary factors being the highest. This is reasonably the case in many practical designs in bio-medicine.

Figure 3: Dose (0,1,2,3,4) finding RCT with males (1) and females(2)

No	Type	Comparison	adjusted p-value
1	Males	1:1 - 0	0.082
2		1:2 - 0	0.302
3		1:3 - 0	0.476
4		1:4 - 0	0.419
5	Females	2:1 - 0	0.451
6		2:2 - 0	0.146
7		2:3 - 0	0.030
8		2:4 - 0	0.070
9	Pooled	p: 1 - 0	0.085
10		p: 2 - 0	0.041
11		p: 3 - 0	0.019
12		p: 4 - 0	0.026

Table 10: Joint Dunnett tests for males, females and pooled data

8 Considering a concomitant covariate

Even in randomized one-way layouts, other continuous covariates X_{ijk} are sometimes observed in addition to the primary endpoint Y_{ijk} . The classic is the baseline value of the primary endpoint or patient characteristic such as age. Although multiple covariates are more typical, only one covariate is considered here, especially from the point of view of possible treatment-by-covariate interaction. Of course, one can easily test a global treatment-by-covariate interaction term in the linear model, but this does not say much about its influence on the treatment vs. control contrasts of interest $\mu_i - C$ alone. Furthermore, a necessary noninferiority test on interaction is hardly used and not very helpful, because the acceptable threshold cannot be determined a priori. Simultaneous confidence intervals (or adjusted p-values) for an arbitrarily chosen grid in the range of values of the covariate per treatment contrast are useful [112]- without any pre-test. In its basic idea, it is somewhat similar to the analysis of a secondary factor in section 7, but just based on a estimations in the linear model for a quantitative covariate. For this approach, the library (*statintcov*) is available in github, which provides simultaneous inference for the difference or ratio to control. The choice of the number of grid points is not too critical, of course it increases the conservatism somewhat. As an example the postweight is the primary endpoint, preweight the covariate in a study to treat anorexia using two treatments (behavioral treatment:CBT and family therapy:FT) in comparison to untreated control (available in library(*statintcov*)). The simultaneous confidence band for a detailed grid is shown for the two ratios to control revealing a significant weight increase for not too underweight girls (i.e. > 80 lbs in FT/Cont). This impressively shows the advantage of the above method compared to the lower confidence limits without consideration of the covariate of 1.007 (CBT/Cont) and 1.051 (FT/Cont).

Figure 4: Analysis of covariance for anorexia data: ratio-to-control

The covariance analysis makes several assumptions, some of which are difficult to test. An obvious violation occurs when both primary endpoint and covariate depend on treatment. An example is organ weight (here liver weight as primary) and terminal body weight of rats in multiple dose toxicological bioassays [55].

Figure 5: Liver weights as primary endpoint and body weight as covariate

For the difference to control, the slopes differs and only for the comparison to the 500 mg dose a decrease for middle body weight are shown. The correct bivariate analysis of liver and body weight [55] reveals a strong liver weight retardation for 500 and 1000 mg. I.e. the above used covariance analysis represents a dangerous false negative result.

9 Mixed effect model

Mixed effect models consider both (at least one) fixed effect factor (to be compared by Dunnett test) and one or more random effects, characterizing sub-unit variability, such as technical replicates, repeated measures (see more in detail chapter 10. Some factors are not independent randomized, but dependent by design, such as timely repeated measures on the same subject, several periods in a cross-over design, replicated measure at the same subject, rats within a cage (or daphnia within a

water tank) [55], paired organs or tissues within an animal, replicates experiments, or dependent by nature, such as litter mates within a pub in reprotoxicological bioassays. There are rather confusing views about when a factor is fixed and when it is random. From the point of view of simultaneous inference here this seems simple: the comparison between the levels of a random factor is not of interest, it is rather modeled appropriately in the variance term.

9.1 Common mixed effect models considering difference of expected values as effect size

The paper on simultaneous inference in general parametric models [66] includes in this general approach the mixed effect models in principle- from asymptotic point of view. That is, designs with small sample sizes, both those of the randomized unit and those of the sub-sampling, can be problematic, both from the convergence of the model fit of the mixed model and the FWER control of the Dunnett test. The minimum requirements for n_i depend on the design, variance ratios, model complexity, and so on- and this in a complex way [82]. From the point of view of the Dunnett test, the treatment contrasts remain unchanged, but the variance estimator and its degree of freedom depend on the chosen random part of the mixed model - in ratio-to-control comparisons, this additionally influences the estimated variance-covariance matrix [114]. As an example a teratogenicity bioassay is used, where 30 female rats were randomly assigned to receive control, low, or high dose of an experimental compound and the pup weights within the litters are modeled (raw data `ratpup` are available in [126]). The R-code for difference-to-control is relatively simple:

```
data("ratpup", package="WWGbook")
library("nlme"); library("multcomp")
mix1 <- lme(weight ~ Treatment, random=~1|litter, data=Ratpup)
plot(glht(mix1, linfct = mcp(Treatment = "Dunnett"), alternative="less")) #### need df satterwhite
```

9.2 Mixed effect model for ratio-to-control inference

But for ratio-to-control comparison both the estimators for fixed effects, and the variance-covariance matrix have to be extracted and the contrast matrix defined:

```
library(mratios)
mix2 <- lme(weight ~ Treatment-1, data=Ratpup,random=~1|litter)
CM2 <- rbind(c(1,0,0),
             c(1,0,0))
DM2 <- rbind(c(0,1,0),
             c(0,0,1))
estm2 <- fixef(mix2)
vcm2 <- vcov(mix2)
plot(gsci.ratio(estm2, vcm2, CM2, DM2,alternative="less", degfree=anova(mix2)[2,2]))
```

Neither the confidence limits for the difference nor for the quotient contain the values of H_0 (i.e. 0 and 1, respectively), i.e. no weight retardation can be detected.

9.3 Generalized mixed effect models: selected effect sizes

Mixed effect models can be used for selected non-normal endpoints accordingly, see details in [55]-chapter 2.1.5.4.1.. By means of the R-function `glmer` within the library `lme4` a proportion (i.e. number of tumors at risk) is modeled for a one-way layout (with the fixed effect factor *dose*) with an additional random factor (i.e. water tanks). This represents an asymptotic approach, i.e. the sample sizes should be large.

10 Treatment comparisons in repeated measures designs

Considering *treatment* and *time* is a specific issue with many modeling strategies. First, time may simply be a secondary randomized factor if the response is measured at different times on different experimental units, e.g. different seedlings in agriculture. Then proceed according to section 7 for interaction in a two-way layout. More common are repeated measures, where the response is measured on the same experimental units (e.g., volunteers in RCTs) at different times. Here, too, a wide variety of approaches are used. On the one hand, one can realize an integral (i.e. summarizing) transformation into a single univariate endpoint for each randomized unit, e.g. estimate an area-under-the-curve (AUC) (also adjusted for incomplete measurements [54] and then evaluate it as a pseudo-variable. On the other hand, one can use a mixed effect model. The mixed model itself is a broad topic with different assumptions of the random variable time, the specification of the correlation between repeated measurements, the selection of different models, the appropriate degree of freedom, heteroscedasticity, the behavior for small n_i , the numerical algorithms, etc.-this is deliberately not elaborated here. In the following, at least the heart-rate example [91] is considered under two assumptions of temporal correlation (auto-regressive model 1st order and simple compound structure) for comparison to the control.

```
library(SimLongi); library(nlme); library(multcomp)
data(heart)
mixM <- lme(heartrate ~ drug, data=heart, random=~1|person, correlation = corAR1())
mixU <- lme(heartrate ~ drug, data=heart, random=~1|person, correlation = corCompSymm())
cM7<-contrMat(table(heart$drug), type = "Dunnett", base=3)
df7=mixM$fixDF$terms[2]
rM <-summary(glht(mixM, linct = cM7, alternative="greater", df=df7 ))
rU <-summary(glht(mixU, linct = cM7, alternative="greater", df=df7))
```

In this example, the resulting adjusted p-values from the two models differ little. Note that this is an asymptotic approach [66], i.e. for small n_i and few time points a level problem may occur [82].

While in the mixed model *time* is considered as a cause of dispersion and inference is performed only with respect to the fixed factor *treatment*, it is also possible to analyze *treatment* and *time* simultaneously, e.g. using *mmm* via combining several marginal, i.e. time-specific, models using the R package *SimLongi* [102]. A modified version for small sample sizes is available [103].

```
library(SimLongi)
data(heart)
SMM<-SimLongiMMM(data=heart, response="heartrate", group="drug",
  time="time", id="person", type="Dunnett",
  base=3, reldist="t")$Results
```

Table 11: Simultaneous Dunnett-type treatment comparison per time point

Comparison	Estimate	SE	LowerCI	UpperCI	Statistic	adjusted p-value
Time1:ax23 - control	-2.25	2.76	-9.89	5.39	-0.81	0.8833
Time1:bww9 - control	9.00	2.97	0.79	17.21	3.03	0.0286
Time2:ax23 - control	8.12	3.13	-0.54	16.79	2.59	0.0703
Time2:bww9 - control	11.62	3.56	1.78	21.47	3.27	0.0172
Time3:ax23 - control	9.50	2.79	1.77	17.23	3.40	0.0129
Time3:bww9 - control	7.12	3.27	-1.91	16.16	2.18	0.1547
Time4:ax23 - control	2.12	2.86	-5.78	10.03	0.74	0.9161
Time4:bww9 - control	8.75	2.95	0.61	16.89	2.97	0.0326

11 Claiming equivalence

11.1 UIT and IUT

Dunnett's test based on the maxT test principle and hence represents an UIT (see some properties in chapter 3.1). The CTP, also for simple treatment comparisons against control based on IUT's within the branches of the closed-under-intersection decision trees (see chapter 6. A combination of IUT, for the tests on equivalence between the directional hypotheses, and UIT, for the tests between the treatment contrasts, represents the simultaneous procedure according to Bofinger [11] [66].

11.2 Equivalence of k treatment levels vs. control

Evidence of equivalence between, for example, a standard therapy and a new therapy is guided in the two-group design by the interval inclusion of the estimated two-sided 90% confidence interval within tolerable threshold limits: 90% because of the two-one-sided-tests (TOST), an IUT. The definition of the tolerable limits is thus inherent, sometimes using the FDA rule [0.8;1.25] in the multiplicative model (mostly based on naive log transformation). Notice, this model is not problem-adequate in most cases. The extension to the comparison with multiple new therapies could be done with two nested IUT's: IUT(IUT), i.e. the equivalence proof of all by the interval inclusion of all 90% intervals, a very conservative method. However, this approach allows only the global proof. For the usual proof of equivalence for one, anyone, new therapy, one can use an nested UIT(IUT) test, where the UIT part is tested using Bonferroni, again conservative (the closed testing version in [109]. Alternatively for a partially balanced design [11] proposed simultaneous confidence intervals based on the k-dimensional t-distribution with a complex correlation matrix consisting of both positive and negative correlations. The Bonferroni-type approach can be used for general unbalanced designs to estimate simultaneous confidence intervals for both difference or ratio to the standard [52], available in library(ETC) [39]. As an example, the efficacy endpoint (change to baseline of HbA1c in week 26) is considered for two doses of canagliflozin compared with sitagliptin as standard therapy for patients with type-2 diabetes [130]. In this nearly balanced, approximate homoscedastic data, the ratio-to-standard simultaneous 95% confidence intervals on equivalence are:

Figure 6: Box-plot and confidence intervals canagliflozin trial

```
library(ETC)
```

```
CITSONG<-etc.rat(C2B~treatment, data=datTSONG, base = 3, margin.up =1.25,  
method = "var.unequal", FWER = 0.05)
```

I.e. equivalence to the standard therapy sitagliptin can be revealed for the 100 mg dose of canagliflozin, but not for the 300 mg dose. On the other hand, claiming non-inferiority represents one-sided testing (based on an a-priori defined tolerable threshold limit) or 95% one-sided confidence limits- in the other direction with respect to claiming superiority. If the interval contains the value of H_0 (i.e., 0 or 1) and is still within the tolerable limits, there is a contradiction of both superiority and equivalence. This is formally prevented by means of expanded intervals [10], e.g. by assigning the lower integer to the value 1 (H_0), as in the above example.

12 Block design

Although completely randomized designs dominate, block designs are also sometimes used to take heterogeneities e.g. between field plots or tanks in aquatic toxicology into account. A simple unreplicated complete block design is considered here, correspondingly more complex designs can be analyzed analogously. Independently of the topic of simultaneous inference, a debate exists whether to model the block as a fixed or random factor [24], [72]. This will not be explored in depth here, but both approaches will be illustrated using real data, with an orientation towards parametric methods. As a first data set the average daily weight gain of steers on three supplementary diets and control, where the barns is considered as block. The adjusted p-values of the fixed effect model (*mod1*) and the random effect model (*mod2*) differ little.

```
library(multcomp); library(SASmixed); library(lme4)
data(AvgDailyGain)
AvgDailyGain$block<-as.factor(AvgDailyGain$Block)
AvgDailyGain$treat<-as.factor(AvgDailyGain$Treatment)
mod1<-lm(adg~treat+block+InitWt, data=AvgDailyGain)
summary(glht(mod1, linfct = mcp(treat = "Dunnett")))
mod2 <- lmer(adg~treat+InitWt+ (1|block) , data=AvgDailyGain)
summary(glht(mod2, linfct = mcp(treat = "Dunnett")))
```

These approaches also work accordingly in the generalized linear (mixed) model, here for the total eklektor counts of brachycera in soil traps in a field trial (data available in library(*BSagri*)).

```
library(BSagri); library(multcomp);library(lme4)
data(Brachycera)
Brachycera$block<-as.factor(Brachycera$Block)
contMat<-contrMat(table(Brachycera$Treatment), type="Dunnett", base=3)
fitqp <- glm(Total ~ Treatment+block, data=Brachycera, family=quasipoisson(link="log"))
summary(glht(fitqp, linfct = mcp(Treatment =contMat)))
fitmM <- glmer(Total~ Treatment + (1|block), data=Brachycera, family=poisson(link="log"))
summary(glht(fitmM, linfct = mcp(Treatment =contMat)))
```

Here, however, the adjusted p-values for comparison vs. standard differ substantially between the fixed effect model assuming a quasi-Poisson link function and the mixed effect model.

13 Multiple analyses of the same data

For many trials there are a range of plausible, closely related analyses of an individual endpoint. For example, the primary analysis of an outcome trial could adjust for certain covariates, make a different choice of covariates, make no covariate adjustment, be conducted on the intent-to-treat (ITT) population or various modified populations, or use various hypothesis testing methods [2]. Clearly, FWER should be controlled for these multiple analyses and max(maxT)-test based on mmm can be used (see further details in chapter 3.2). As a simple example the litter weight data in the package multcomp is used, where two concomitant covariates litter size and gestation time can be considered. Four models are used: i) without a covariate, ii) with litter size as covariate, iii) with gestation time as covariate and iv) with both covariates:

From a model selection perspective model 4 should be used (smallest AICc value), but for a risk assessment perspective model 1 : even is significant decrease. Notice, the above example may be biased because both covariates may be dose-dependent (see chapter 8).

Table 12: Multiple analyses of the same data

Comparisons	Test stats	p-value
Without: 5 - 0	-2.16	0.153
Without: 50 - 0	-1.74	0.347
Without: 500 - 0	-1.86	0.277
ONLY1: 5 - 0	-2.64	0.047
ONLY1: 50 - 0	-1.33	0.618
ONLY1: 500 - 0	-2.23	0.130
ONLY2: 5 - 0	-2.12	0.167
ONLY2: 50 - 0	-2.11	0.170
ONLY2: 500 - 0	-1.64	0.408
BOTH12: 5 - 0	-2.60	0.054
BOTH12: 50 - 0	-1.71	0.362
BOTH12: 500 - 0	-2.00	0.211

14 Evaluation of multiple endpoints in k-sample designs

Although univariate analysis of several (multiple) endpoints using several Dunnett's test, each at level α is dominant, multiple correlated, possible differently-scales endpoints are also tested jointly. Especially in clinical studies, specific motivations exist for this, e.g. co-primary endpoints (where the claim is to demonstrate success for all endpoints by an IUT), or primary endpoints, where at least one, anyone endpoint demonstrates success. A quite different issue is the use of a multivariate tests alone to claim combined information of many low informative endpoints, e.g. in genetics.

The focus here is the joint analysis of some (2, 3, 4) primary endpoints allowing the interpretation of the underlying marginal hypotheses, i.e. the interpretation per endpoint of interest. Two different approaches are considered: i) closed testing procedure for complex marginal hypotheses containing both between treatment contrasts and between endpoints comparisons (CTP), ii) double maximum tests (max(maxT)-test), again for both treatments and endpoints inference.

14.1 CTP for multiple endpoints

CTP can be formulate for any elementary hypotheses not only for *between treatments* as in chapter 6, but also for *both between treatments and between endpoints* [62]. Table 13 shows such a CTP for a simple design $[C, T_1, T_2]$ and 2 endpoints(A, B) with elementary hypotheses, intersection hypotheses (where non-overlapping are denoted as partition hypotheses) and global hypotheses (where T1-T4 characterize the branch in the CTP-tree; pCT ... pairwise contrast test, pComb ... Fisher-style p-value combination test):

Table 13: Bivariate Dunnett-type CTP

No.	Type	H_0	Test	Branch
1	Elementary	$H_{CT_1}^A$	$pCT_{CT_1}^A$	B1
2	Elementary	$H_{CT_2}^A$	$pCT_{CT_2}^A$	B2
3	Elementary	$H_{CT_1}^B$	$pCT_{CT_1}^B$	B3
4	Elementary	$H_{CT_2}^B$	$pCT_{CT_2}^B$	B4
5	Intersection of 2	$H_{CT_1}^A : H_{CT_2}^A \Rightarrow H_{CT_{12}}^A$	$\min(Du^A)$	B1,B2
6	Intersection of 2	$H_{CT_1}^A : H_{CT_1}^B \Rightarrow H_{CT_1}^{AB}$	$bivariateT_{CT_1}$	B1,B3
7	Partition of 2	$H_{CT_1}^A : H_{CT_2}^B$	$pComb(pCT_{CT_1}^A, pCT_{CT_2}^B)$	B1,B4
8	Intersection of 2	$H_{CT_2}^A : H_{CT_2}^B \Rightarrow H_{CT_2}^{AB}$	$bivariateT_{CT_2}$	B2,B4
9	Intersection of 2	$H_{CT_1}^B : H_{CT_2}^B \Rightarrow H_{CT_{12}}^B$	$\min(Du^B)$	B3,B4
10	Partition of 2	$H_{CT_2}^A : H_{CT_1}^B$	$pComb(pCT_{CT_2}^A, pCT_{CT_1}^B)$	B2,B3
11	Partition of 3	$H_{CT_1}^A : H_{CT_2}^A : H_{CT_1}^B \Rightarrow H_{CT_{12}}^A : H_{CT_1}^B$	$pComb(\min(Du^A), pCT_{CT_1}^B)$	B1,B2,B3
12	Partition of 3	$H_{CT_1}^A : H_{CT_2}^A : H_{CT_2}^B \Rightarrow H_{CT_{12}}^A : H_{CT_2}^B$	$pComb(\min(Du^A), pCT_{CT_2}^B)$	B1,B2,B4
13	Partition of 3	$H_{CT_2}^A : H_{CT_1}^A : H_{CT_2}^B \Rightarrow H_{CT_2}^A : H_{CT_{12}}^B$	$pComb(pCT_{CT_2}^A, \min(Du^B))$	B2,B3,B4
14	Partition of 3	$H_{CT_1}^A : H_{CT_1}^B : H_{CT_2}^B \Rightarrow H_{CT_1}^A : H_{CT_{12}}^B$	$pComb(pCT_{CT_1}^A, \min(Du^B))$	B1,B2,B4
15	Global Global	$H_{CT_1}^A : H_{CT_2}^B : H_{CT_2}^A : H_{CT_2}^B \Rightarrow H_{CT_{12}}^A : H_{CT_{12}}^B$ $\Rightarrow H_{CT_{12}}^{AB}$	$\min(Du^{AB})$	B1,B2,B3,B4

Notice, the nice properties of a complete family of hypotheses in chapter 6 are lost and the structure of the CTP tree becomes complex including partition hypotheses, i.e. non-overlapping intersection hypotheses. Thus, not only uni-, bi- and tri-variate tests for the 2 and k sample problem are necessary, but also for the specific partition hypotheses for non-overlapping hypotheses, e.g. $H_{01}^{12} : H_{02}^2$, which

are tested here using Fisher’s product criterion ($pComb$). The already complex system of this simple example shows that CTP is practically limited to only a few comparisons to control (2, 3, or 4) and only a few endpoints 2,3, or 4. In the elementary hypotheses, instead of pairwise t-tests, multiple contrasts for $\mu_i - \mu_0$ are used (pCT) [39, 55], which exploit the entire df , a significant power advantage especially for small n_i (at the price of assuming homogeneous variances). To avoid directional errors, CTP’s are formulated for one-sided hypotheses here.

Several multivariate global tests are available, e.g. the parametric and the rank-based version of O’Briens tests [98]. Alternatively, uni-directional permutation tests based on pairwise distance (or similarity) measures (Euclidean or maximum absolute difference) between sample elements ([5], [80]) are considered here. For the test in the three sample design $[C; T1; T2]$, the averages of between-group pairs were calculated separately for $[C; T1]$ and $[C; T2]$ and the maximum of both has been used as test statistics in the permutation test [23].

Both CTP and maxT test become more conservative with increasing number of elementary hypotheses. Controlling FWER, this implies an inherent power loss compared to a single test. In the maxT test, this is determined by the number q of individual tests in the ξ -variate t-distribution, with the correlation between the tests having a conservatism-reducing effect. In contrast, the conservativeness of the CTP is due to that of the underlying IUT in the branches of the CTP decision tree, whereas the correlation between the individual tests is not considered in that univariate distribution. Furthermore, the number and type of individual tests in the IUT’s depends on the specific structure of the CTP tree. If the number of individual tests is too high within each IUT (and e.g. 10 are quickly reached in real applications), it becomes hopelessly conservative - a limitation of the CTP in principle to low dimensional cases.

As an example, a standard extracorporeal circulation set (S) heart surgery is compared with a heparine covering version (H) and a biocompatible surface configuration (B) for the three primary endpoints thrombocyte counts, tartrate resistant acid phosphatase (TRAP) and platelet function (ADP) [81], see the boxplot in Figure 7. The raw data are available in the CRAN package SimComp. Because of the near-to-balanced design, variance heterogeneity is ignored in the following analysis to keep the issue simple. The adjusted p-values for 5 approaches are reported in Table 14 (bold ... significant). Because within the the CTP’s, the global test is not significant, no adjusted p-value can be smaller than 0.05 and therefore the complex tree structure is not shown in this table. Only for one primary endpoint, ADP, a significant increase can be shown for the comparison B vs. S using the mmm and maxT test methods. The related R-code for the 5 tests is (where the function $p_{distance_k,group}$ can

Figure 7: Box plots heart surgery extracorporeal circulation set example

be find in [62]):

library(SimComp)

```

data(coagulation)
#### max(maxT)
comp2 <- SimTestDiff(data=coagulation, grp="Group", resp=c("Thromb.count","ADP","TRAP"),
                    type="Dunnett", base=3, alternative="greater", covar.equal=FALSE)

summary(comp2)
##### mmm
library(multcomp)
coagulation$Group <- relevel(coagulation$Group, ref = "S")
mod1<-lm(Thromb.count~Group, data=coagulation)
mod2<-lm(ADP~Group, data=coagulation)
mod3<-lm(TRAP~Group, data=coagulation)
TUWI<- glht(mmm(Th=mod1, Ad=mod2, Tr=mod3), mlf(mcp(Group = "Dunnett")), alternative="greater")
summary(TUWI)
##### contrast pairwise
Cmat2<-c(-1,0,1) # 3sample pairwise
Cmat1<-c(-1,1,0)
PP1<-summary(glht(mod1, linfct = mcp(Group =Cmat1), alternative="greater"))$test$pvalues
PP2<-summary(glht(mod1, linfct = mcp(Group =Cmat2), alternative="greater"))$test$pvalues
PP3<-summary(glht(mod2, linfct = mcp(Group =Cmat1), alternative="greater"))$test$pvalues
PP4<-summary(glht(mod2, linfct = mcp(Group =Cmat2), alternative="greater"))$test$pvalues
PP5<-summary(glht(mod3, linfct = mcp(Group =Cmat1), alternative="greater"))$test$pvalues
PP6<-summary(glht(mod3, linfct = mcp(Group =Cmat2), alternative="greater"))$test$pvalues
PP<-c(PP1,PP2,PP3,PP4,PP5,PP6)
##### OBrien
library(CombinePValue); library(robustHD); library(simstudy)
coagulation$S1<-standardize(coagulation$Thromb.count, centerFun = mean, scaleFun = sd)
coagulation$S2<-standardize(coagulation$ADP, centerFun = mean, scaleFun = sd)
coagulation$S3<-standardize(coagulation$TRAP, centerFun = mean, scaleFun = sd)
coagulation$S123<-coagulation$S1+coagulation$S2+coagulation$S3
mod7 <- lm(S123~Group, data = coagulation) # OBrien parametric
PP7<-summary(glht(mod7, linfct = mcp(Group ="Dunnett"), alternative="greater"))$test$pvalues
### distance tests
XX<-as.matrix(coagulation[, c(2:4)])
gr<-as.numeric(coagulation$Group)
grpsel <- c(1,2,3)
KK <- p_distance_kgroup(XX,gr,grpsel,1,1,1,399) # new Kropf test 1 global 2 01 3 02
KK4 <- p_distance_kgroup(XX,gr,grpsel,4,1,1,399) # new Kropf test 4 global 2 01 3 02

```

Table 14: Adjusted one-sided p-values for 5 approaches

No	Comparison	mmm	maxT	Bonferroni	CTP-OBrienparametric	CTP-distance test (max component)
1	Thromb: B - S	0.38	0.32	0.76	max(0.08,...,0.13)	max(0.06,...,0.13)
2	Thromb: H - S	0.73	0.73	0.99	max(0.08,...,0.34)	max(0.06,...,0.34)
3	ADP: B - S	0.03	0.04	0.05	max(0.08,...,0.008)	max(0.06,...,0.008)
4	ADP: H - S	0.44	0.38	0.94	max(0.08,...,0.16)	max(0.06,...,0.16)
5	TRAP: B - S	0.58	0.59	0.99	max(0.08,...,0.23)	max(0.06,...,0.23)
6	TRAP: H - S	0.69	0.70	0.99	max(0.08,...,0.31)	max(0.06,...,0.31)

14.2 Max(maxT)-test for Dunnett-type comparisons of primary end-points

Multiple contrast tests for correlated endpoints can be formulated as max(maxT) test, i.e. maximum test regarding the treatment-vs.-control comparisons and maximum test regarding the multiple endpoints. In a first solution, the approximate correlation matrix is estimated from both the calculated correlations between the treatment contrasts and the empirical Pearson correlation between the endpoints [40, 41, 42, 43]. Adjusted p-values or simultaneous confidence intervals for both differences and ratios (for control) can be estimated with the CRAN package *SimComp*. Alternatively, the variance-covariance matrix is obtained from the asymptotic joint distributions of parameter estimates from multiple marginal models [106]. The function mmm is available in the CRAN package *multcomp* [52]. In the context of multiple endpoints, this approach was used for multiple binary endpoints in

both 2- and k-sample design [74], for multiple and repeated measures endpoints [71, 102], for multiple normal distributed, proportions and different-scaled endpoints [55] (in chapters 2.4.4., 3.6.1. and 5.4), for composite and their marginal endpoints [110], as well for multiple time-to-event endpoints by the Wei-Lachin test [7]- probably the first mmm approach. A significant advantage is the possibility of a combined analysis of differently scaled endpoints. Of course, adjusted p-values or simultaneous confidence intervals are available for the elementary hypotheses of interest. Compared to the CTP, the restrictions on small number of treatments and/or small number of correlated endpoints are less strict here.

14.2.1 Comparing of CTP with Max(maxT)-test- results of a simulation study

In a simulation study, three power definitions (i) the common any-pairs power, ii) all-pairs power, iii) individual pairs power) were considered for several types of alternatives [62]

The power of max(maxT) test depends seriously on the complex correlation matrix: is equal to that of the Bonferroni test for correlations near to 0, otherwise near to the power of level α marginal tests for correlations near to 1- the reality is somewhere in between. Furthermore, the more endpoints and treatment, the more conservative are all tests. The widespread expectation of power increase by multiple endpoints (compared to the analysis of single endpoints) is only fulfilled by the concept of any pairs power (and actually by their any condition) and only under specific conditions regarding correlations and noncentralities- and only to a modest extent from a practical view (e.g. needed sample sizes). Considering individual powers (the most fair definition), in any configuration a price for multiplicity adjustment have to be paid. Summarizing the max(max)T-test (mmm) can be recommended (with respect to CTP): i) it is as powerful as CTP's using summarizing global tests, ii) revealing high power when not all endpoint contribute to H_1 , especially high for not to too low correlations, iii) simultaneous confidence intervals (and adjusted p-value) are available, iv) this approach is available for different scaled endpoints, v) software is available in the CRAN package multcomp, and vi) both global and individual claims are available.

14.3 Max(maxT)-test for Dunnett-type comparisons of differently-scaled endpoints

Most work on the analysis of multiple endpoints assumes that they are equally distributed, even normally distributed with homogeneous variances, more even unidirectional and sometimes even identically scale-transformed. In practice, differently scaled endpoints occur, such as normal and time-to-event or binomials and counts. Since the mmm method is generally based on glm's, it is easy to apply here, the more so the correlations between differently scaled endpoints are by no means trivial. A related example is the bivariate test on normal (pup weight) and binomial endpoint (malformation rate) in [55] (chapter 5.4).

15 Simultaneous inference using generalized estimating equation model (GEE)

Simultaneous inference for different-scaled correlated multiple endpoints in the presence of repeated observations can be achieved by generalized estimating equation model (GEE) in combination with the multiple marginal model approach which fit for each endpoint marginally, taking into account dependencies within the same subject. See for more details [107] and the R package *mmmgee*.

```
<<RepeatedMultipleEndpointsGEE, echo=TRUE,results='asis', warning=FALSE, message=FALSE, cache=TRUE>>=
library(mmmgee)
data(keratosi)
m1<-geem2(clearance~trt,id=id,data=keratosi,
```

```

        family=binomial,corstr="independence")
m2<-geem2(pain~trt,id=id,data=keratosis[keratosis$lesion==1,],
        family=gaussian,corstr="exchangeable")
L1<-L2<-diag(1,4)[-1,]
MGE<-mmmgee.test(x=list(m1,m2),L=list(L1,L2),alternative="less",
        conf.int=TRUE,denomDF=40, statistic="Wald",
        type="maximum",biascorr=TRUE,
asymptotic=FALSE,closed.test=TRUE)
mge<-as.data.frame(MGE$test$closed.test)[, c(2,5)]
@

```

16 Joint analysis of sub-groups and the overall population

Several types of analysis of a priori defined subgroups in randomized phase III clinical trials are performed, among them to demonstrate efficacy in both overall population and a targeted subgroup or even any subgroup. A somewhat conservative UIT-style approach (extendable for correlated multiple endpoints) was proposed [124] using again the mmm approach, see chapter 3.2. The trick to model subgroups using the overall data as needed in mmm is the used of the missing option *na.action = na.exclude*. In [124] an example with a two-arm trial and multiple endpoints is discussed, whereas an extension to k-sample design with comparisons against control is straightforward within this framework.

17 Testing more than just location shifts

17.1 Most likely transformation models

Since the Dunnett test is defined for $\epsilon = N(\mu, \sigma^2)$, there is a desire for robust variants, especially because pre-test selection methods tend to be problematic [75]. Particularly, robustness with respect to variance heterogeneity, violation of the normal distribution due to skewness and outlier are primarily considered. In this context, variance heterogeneity seems to be particularly relevant, since it is present in real data. Besides the violation of the FWER, the bias in treatments with homogeneous variance is, see eg. chapter 4 especially critical. When violation of normal distribution is considered both nonparametric procedure (see chapter 18.1 and those with robust estimators, such as M-estimators, can be used [61].

A more general robust approach is the most likely transformation method [68] which based on several transformation models and allows to select the most appropriate model using an maximum likelihood framework. Thereby, the parameterization of the monotonically increasing transformation function is achieved by Bernstein polynomials, which can be used to approximate arbitrary continuous distributions. While the usual regression models estimate the conditional mean as a function of the factor or the covariate and assume that other distribution properties like variance or skewness of the distribution are neglected, these are exactly taken into account in the MLT approach. Therefore, this is robust to arbitrary non-normal distributions (including discreteness), variance heterogeneity, extreme values, and even censored observations (e.g., values with a detection limit). A related CRAN package *mlt* is available [65]. This mlt-approach can be used for simultaneous comparisons versus control [61] for the odds ratio following the continuous outcome logistic model approach [88]. The latter allows a scale-independent interpretation due to the effect size odds ratio, which is particularly advantageous when comparing multiple endpoints.

17.2 Comparing variances

Only few approaches for the comparison of sample variances of k treatment groups with those of the control are available [84, 86]. A simple approach is the use of the Levene transformation $abs(y_{ij} - median(y_i))$ in the linear model [32, 93]. Using Shirley's reaction data [120], a higher sample variance

in the second dose group results with respect to control.

Figure 8: Shirley reaction times example

```
library(nparcomp)
data(reaction)
reaction$Dose<-as.factor(reaction$Group)

medreac<-tapply(reaction$Time, reaction$Dose, median) # group-specific medians
medRC<-medreac[as.integer(reaction$Dose)] # median for each subject
reaction$tTime<- abs(reaction$Time-medRC) # Levene transformation

library(multcomp)
mod1<-lm(tTime~Dose, data=reaction)
Scale <- summary(glht(mod1, linfct=mcp(Dose ="Dunnett")))
```

Table 15: Scale procedure

No	Comparison	test statistics	p-value
1	1 - 0	2.08	0.11
2	2 - 0	2.72	0.03
3	3 - 0	1.78	0.20

17.3 Location-scale alternatives

There are situations where heterogeneous variances are not considered as a confounding variable to be adjusted away, but are considered as an early detection criterion in addition to the location effect. This can be modeled as the sum of locations and scale effects in the sense of Lepage [85], see [93, 94], or as a $\max(\max T)$ test using the mmm approach (see chapter 3.2), simultaneously modeling both location effects and scale effects (simply Levene-transformed endpoint as in chapter 17.2 [59]). Elementary decisions for both the individual treatment-vs.-control comparisons for both location and scale effects are available as adjusted p-values or simultaneous confidence intervals. Again for the reaction times examples:

```
library(multcomp)
mod1<-lm(tTime~Dose, data=reaction)
mod2<-lm(Time~Dose, data=reaction)
JointLS <- glht(mmm(scale = mod1, location= mod2), mlf(mcp(Dose ="Dunnett")))
JTLS<-summary(JointLS)
```

Increasing location effects can be seen in the mid and high dose, as well as an increased variability in the mid dose.

18 Dunnett tests for non-normal distributed endpoints

Three issues are discussed for non-normal endpoints: i) nonparametric tests, using relative effect size estimators, ii) using of specific link functions in glm or even glmm, such as for proportions, and iii) simple data transformation, such

Table 16: Location-scale procedure

No	Comparison	test statistics	p-value
1	scale: 1 - 0	2.08	0.17
2	scale: 2 - 0	2.72	0.03
3	scale: 3 - 0	1.78	0.30
4	location: 1 - 0	2.20	0.13
5	location: 2 - 0	3.20	0.01
6	location: 3 - 0	4.80	0.00

as log- or arcsin transformation. All these approaches are valid only asymptotically [66], i.e. care is needed when using small n_i .

18.1 Nonparametric approaches

Nonparametric Dunnett-type tests are applied by users under the assumption that they are robust to all possible deviations from the normal distribution. Unfortunately, this is only partially the case. Often they are biased especially for heterogeneous variances (in unbalanced designs), are defined for continuous distributions and therefore have problems for ties or discrete data, are asymptotic tests with corresponding problems for small n_i . In addition, effect sizes are difficult to interpret and confidence intervals are hard to obtain. First, the historical tests are briefly presented, followed by the method of relative effect sizes.

18.1.1 Pairwise vs. k-ranking procedures

Nonparametric many-to-one tests in one-way layouts can be classified into pairwise-ranking (Wilcoxon rank sums) [27] and joint-ranking approaches (Kruskal–Wallis ranking) [99]. Notice, the fundamental problem of k-ranking approaches is their dependence of the effect estimator $\phi_{i,0}$ under consideration from the other estimators on the other estimators $\phi_{l,0}, l \neq i$ not regarded.

18.1.2 Relative effect size estimator

The joint-pseudo-ranking approach for relative effects provides adjusted p-value and simultaneous confidence intervals, is defined for discrete distributions as well and allows variance heterogeneity. The relative effect sizes are proportions $p_{0,i} = Pr(X_i < X_0) + \frac{1}{2}Pr(X_i = X_0)$ (where $p_{0,i} = 0$ at the null hypothesis H_0^i). Analogously to the parametric approach a maxT test can be formulated for $l \in (1, \dots, q)$ multiple contrasts $T_l = \sqrt{N} \frac{\hat{p}_l - 0.5}{\sqrt{\hat{v}_l}}$ with $p_l = \int (\sum |c_{li}| F_i) d(\sum c_{lj} F_j)$. The $T_{max} = \max(T_1, \dots, T_q)$ follows jointly an approximate q -variate normal distribution $z_{q,two-sided,1-\alpha,R}$ with correlation matrix R . R is estimated from n_i, c_i and sample specific variances [78] without the common product-moment structure. For small sample size an approximate t-distributed version with related Welch-type df^* [18] is highly recommended. Related confidence intervals are available:

$$Pr \left(\hat{p}_l - t_{k,df^*,two-sided,1-\alpha,R} \sqrt{\frac{v_l}{N}} \leq p_l \leq \hat{p}_l + t_{k,df^*,two-sided,1-\alpha,R} \sqrt{\frac{v_l}{N}} \right) \rightarrow (1 - \alpha)$$

whereas a $[0, 1]$ range preventing transformations can be recommended, e.g., the logit transformation, available in the package *nparcomp* [79]. The reaction time example was analysed by Dunnett-type relative effect sizes in chapter 18.3; here are the related simultaneous confidence intervals:

Figure 9: Reaction time data: Simultaneous confidence intervals for relative effect sizes

18.2 Proportions

18.2.1 Using canonical link function, yielding $\log(\text{OR})$ as effect size

In an object-oriented language such as R, the analysis of properties in a glm-object is similarly simple as that of an lm-object (see chapter 3.1.4). Proportions can be analyzed as 2 by k tables (a summary statistic) or directly from the raw data with the format yes/no (or 0,1) for the occurrence or non-occurrence of the event of interest. For example, the 2-by-5 table data for presence or absence of an adverse event in dose-dependent suppression of serum prolactin by cabergoline [14]:

```
webs<-data.frame(
  dose = c(0,0.125, 0.5, 0.75, 1),
  present = c(9, 19,21,21,24),
  absent = c(11, 24, 21, 21,17))
webs$Dose<-as.factor(webs$dose)
library(multcomp)
supOR <-glm(cbind(present, absent)~Dose, data=webs,family= binomial(link="logit"))
summary(glht(supOR, linfct = mcp(Dose = "Dunnett"), alternative="greater"))
```

The object `supOR` contains the estimators for the fixed effects and the variance-covariance, used by the function `glht()`. Notice the the specific endpoint format `glm(cbind(yes,no)`. This table data format can be extended to a raw data format alternatively:

```
adverse <-c(rep("absent",11), rep("present",9), rep("absent",24), rep("present",19),
  rep("absent",21),rep("present",21),rep("absent",21),rep("present",21),
  rep("absent",17),rep("present",24))
dose <-c(rep(0, 20), rep(0.125, 43),rep(0.5, 42),rep(0.75, 42), rep(1, 41))
webster <-data.frame(adverse,dose)
webster$adv<-as.factor(webster$adverse)
webster$Dose<-as.factor(webster$dose)
lmW <-glm(adv~Dose, data=webster, family= binomial(link="logit"))
summary(glht(lmW, linfct = mcp(Dose = "Dunnett"),alternative="greater"))
```

Using the canonical link function, the effect size is $\log(\text{OR})$, which needs some help for interpreting the results by non-statisticians.

18.2.2 Difference of proportions as effect size

Although the use of `library(addreg)` to fit additive identity-link binomial regression models by a stable combinatorial EM algorithm [25] is a more general approach, risk difference as effect size can be under some conditions (e.g., the number of iterations should be large) used by common GLM with identity link.

```
library(tukeytrend)
library(logbin, quietly=TRUE)
swaOR <-glm(cbind(events+0.5,(n-events)+0.5)~dose, data=squam,
```

```

    family= binomial(link="logit"))#
tuOR <- tukeytrendfit(swaOR, dose="dose", scaling=c("ari", "ord", "arilog"))
pOR <- summary(glht(model=tuOR$mmm, linfct=tuOR$mlf, alternative="greater"))
swaRD <- glm(formula(swaOR), data = squam,family=binomial(link="identity"),maxit=500)
tuRD <- tukeytrendfit(swaRD, dose="dose", scaling=c("ari", "ord", "arilog"))
pRD <- summary(glht(model=tuRD$mmm, linfct=tuRD$mlf, alternative="greater"))
swaRR<-logbin(cbind(events,(n-events))~dose, data=squam, warn=FALSE)
tuRR <- tukeytrendfit(swaRR, dose="dose", scaling=c("ari", "ord", "arilog"))
pRR <- summary(glht(model=tuRR$mmm, linfct=tuRR$mlf, alternative="greater"))
ttany <- combtt(tuOR, tuRD,tuRR)
anylink<-summary(glht(model=ttany$mmm, linfct=ttany$mlf, alternative="greater"))
@

<<PrintTukeytrendProp, echo=FALSE,results='asis', warning=FALSE, message=FALSE>>=
library(xtable)
library(ggplot2)
tOR <-fortify(pOR)[, c(1,6)]
tRD <-fortify(pRD)[, c(1,6)]
tRR <-fortify(pRR)[, c(1,6)]
tany <-fortify(anylink)[6, c(1,6)]
tall<-rbind(tOR,tRD,tRR,tany)
EffectSize<-c(rep("OR", 3), rep("RD", 3), rep("RR",3), rep("Opt:RD",1))
Metameter<- c(rep(c("ari","ord", "log"), 3), "Opt:log")
Tall<-cbind(EffectSize,Metameter, tall[, 2])
colnames(Tall) <-c("Effect size", "Metameter", "$p$-value")
print(xtable(Tall, digits=4, caption="Any effect size, any metameter", size="\small",
    label="tab:tp6"), include.rowname=FALSE, caption.placement = "top", sanitize.text.function =
@

```

The optimal model without a-priori model choice (Opt: RD) is for RD and $\log(D_i)$, where the p-value of 0.0013 is only slightly higher than for the a-priori selected model (0.00068).

Ratios of proportions (risk ratios) can be used as effect size by the package *logbin* using an EM-type algorithm [26] or the *library(logbin)* fits relative risk regression models using the log-binomial model [25].

18.2.3 Using adjusted cell estimates as a small n_i approximation

In quite a few applications, both the number of cases n_i and/or the number of events r_i are so small that the validity of the asymptotic methods is questionable. Exactly then approximative adjustments, like the Yates correction, have been used quite successfully since the earliest times of the analysis of 2 by 2 table data. Particularly, when the control rate is near-to-zero and/or small n_i occur, adding two successes and two failures to the table data achieve pseudo-scores intervals [4], i.e. instead the ML estimators $p_i = r_i/n_i$, adjusted estimators $\tilde{p}_i = (r_i + \varsigma)/(n_i + 2\varsigma)$ are used, with e.g. $\varsigma = 1$. This introduces a bias, but the confidence interval better maintains the 95% level, quite different for one-sided limits or two-sided intervals [116, 113]. A further approaches are the Newcombe hybrid scores or the MOVER available in the CRAN packages *binMto* and *pairwiseCI*

18.3 Log-transformed primary endpoint

Logarithmic transformation of the sometimes skewed and heteroscedastic primary endpoint before Dunnett-type analysis is common, in bioinformatics even the non-comment standard approach today. This trivial method, however, has it all. Not only does one switch from the additive to the multiplicative model, but one also transforms the empirical distribution itself, i.e. not only the location but also the variance and the effect size is the ratio of medians. As an alternative, simultaneous confidence intervals for both difference- and ratio-to-control are available using the generalized pivotal quantities methods (GPQ) which control FWER also for small n_i [111], available in the *library(MCPAN)*. The complexity of the analysis is demonstrated by the reaction time example in *library(nparcomp)* [79]:

rather different ratio-to-control effect sizes and their lower 95% confidence limits are compared: for i) GPG and its competing approaches ii) log-transformed Dunnett test, iii) normal Dunnett-type test, iv) nonparametric MCT (see chapter 18.1 and v) most likely transformation (see chapter 17.1) The quite different effect sizes are i) ratio of log-normals, ii) ratio of medians, iii) ratio of arithmetic means, iii) relative effect size ($H_0 = 0.5$) and iv) odds ratio.

Comparison	GPQ	log-transformed	normal	relative effect size	Odds ratio mlt
$D_1/0$	1.9[1.2,]	1.7[1.04,]	1.9[0.97,]	0.88[0.59,]	8.5[1.3,]
$D_2/0$	2.4[1.5,]	2.1[1.3,]	2.3[1.2,]	0.89[0.58,]	20.7[2.2,]
$D_3/0$	3.1[2.1,]	2.8[1.7,]	3.0[1.7,]	0.96[0.69,]	85.2[7.5,]

Table 17: Ratio-to-control inference for competing approaches to naive log-transformation

Although not comparable, the effect sizes for the 3 contrasts differ significantly among the 5 methods, even more so the extent of the lower confidence limits into the alternative, with even incompatible decisions ($D_1/0$ is not significantly increased for normal ratios).

19 Related multiple contrast tests

Since the Dunnett test was presented as a special case of MCT, different special cases should be considered comparatively: i) all-pair comparisons [69] (an extension from many-to-one to all-pairs comparisons and one/two-sided to two-sided), ii) comparisons against the total mean [100] (an extension from comparison vs. a single control to comparisons vs. total mean), iii) control vs. dose group comparisons under order restriction [129], and iv) user-defined comparisons [55]. The special case has to be selected, which ensures the error control for exactly the comparisons of interest- depending on the present design and the present experimental question.

19.1 The Williams test: comparing of dose group against control under order restriction

The Williams test [129], originally introduced using maximum likelihood estimators under order restriction (in- or excluding the control group) can also be presented as a special case of an MCT [15], which is illustrated by a specific contrast matrix:

c_i	C	D_1	D_2
c_a	-1	0	1
c_b	-1	1/2	1/2

Table 18: Williams test (one-sided) [12]

The differences between Dunnett and William's test are: i) the Dunnett's test can consider treatment groups (unordered) or doses (ordered), the Williams test only doses, ii) the Dunnett's test considers the inference between C and the individual T_i treatment or D_i , whereas the Williams test does not consider explicit doses but pooled doses (except for $D_{max} - C$), iii) both tests can be formulated one- or two-sided, but a two-sided hypothesis formulation together with a trend assumption seems to be problematic for the Williams-test, iv) their closed tests differ substantially due to the order restriction, v) The Williams test is sometimes only used as a global test for monotonic trend, a Dunnett global test (any T_i is different from C) hardly ever, vi) both tests have e different characteristics in estimating the NOAEL.

For the evaluation of designs $[C, D_1, \dots, D_q]$, e.g. in regulatory toxicology, guidance recommends the use of Dunnett and/or Williams test [1]. It is not clear which test is used for which situation. It is possible to formulate a maxT test for both tests together, thus obtaining the two different statements

[70]. The joint test becomes more conservative, which is low due to the considerable correlation between the similar individual tests. However, the statement becomes more comprehensive. This is a good example for a compromise between as few individual tests as possible, which are highly correlated, and as broad an interpretability as possible (see above, see furthermore joint Tukey and Williams trend test [115]).

c_i	C	D_1	D_2
c_a	-1	0	1
c_b	-1	1	0
c_c	-1	0	1
c_d	-1	1/2	1/2

Table 19: DunnettWilliams (one-sided) test [51]

19.2 CTP under order restriction as an alternative to the Williams test

Although the elementary hypotheses of CTPs in unrestricted design (Dunnett) and order restricted design (Williams) are the same, e.g. for a simple $k = 2 + 1$ example:

$$H_0^{01} : \mu_0 = \mu_1$$

$$H_0^{02} : \mu_0 = \mu_2$$

$$H_0^{03} : \mu_0 = \mu_3$$

under strict order restriction (and homoscedasticity) a shortcut exists:

if H_0^{0123} is rejected, than H_0^{03} is rejected per definition (without testing) as well,

and if H_0^{012} is rejected, H_0^{02} is rejected as well, i.e.

$$H_0^{0123} \Rightarrow H_0^{012} \Rightarrow H_0^{01}$$

whereas for each hypotheses global or partial global Williams test (not all contrasts) are used [49]. The disadvantage of difficult confidence intervals and the non-interpretability of individual doses remains. This can be achieved by a step-down use of pairwise contrasts instead of William's test, which is extremely simple and only somewhat power-reduced.

Notice, this step-down CTP $H_0^{0123} \Rightarrow H_0^{012} \Rightarrow H_0^{01}$ works with other global trend tests as well, e.g. the Armitage test [6] for proportions or the nonparametric Jonckheere test [95].

20 Miscellaneous

20.1 Dunnett test and ANOVA

The term 'post hoc test' is frequently used in application publications, meaning the use of Dunnett's test (or other MCP's) after ANOVA (conditional on global significance or not), e.g. for the comparison of four treatment groups and the control in an in-vivo study for anti-angiogenic activity [73]. In the one-way layout, an unconditional ANOVA pre-test is not harmful but superfluous, both in the sense of a procedure, but particularly in the sense of interpretation. The conditional ANOVA pre-test, on the other hand, can even be problematic, since the alternative space of the ANOVA F-test is wider than that of the Dunnett test (especially with one-sided formulation). In the case of factorial designs, there might be some arguments in favor of an ANOVA pretest. The joint test of level-specific and global tests, demonstrated in section 7 shows the inappropriateness of this. Thus, in summary, the recommendation remains: *The two-step approach - a significant ANOVA F-test before Dunnett's comparisons against a control - is not recommended* [50]

20.2 Stepwise procedures

Stepwise (step-up, down) [30, 122] or weighted [16] procedures occupy a relatively large space in the literature. Here, these are discussed only very briefly, since interpretable simultaneous confidence

intervals are difficult to estimate [117, 35]. Holm's basic idea [47] is the stepwise dimensional reduction of the remaining decision space into the Bonferroni test (without taking correlation into account), after excluding the tests with smaller p-values that clearly no longer produce an alpha error. A further special case are adaptive designs with possible treatment selection in randomized clinical trials [76].

20.3 Comparing against a fixed standard value instead against the negative control data

There are situations where instead of the usual comparison against the control values, you want to compare against a vector of fixed standard values. Then j different independent one-samples t-tests are considered $t_j = (x_j - x_j^0)/s_j\sqrt{(1/n_j)}$. A global test over all t_j can be formulated as a maxT test $T = \max(t_1, \dots, t_k)$. According to Gabriel's theorem [31] of monotone quantiles $t_{k,df,R,1-\alpha}$ of the joint distribution, both adjusted p-values p_j and simultaneous confidence intervals CI_j are available for this purpose. Since k independent samples X_{ij} are assumed, the t_j are uncorrelated and thus $t_{k,df_j,R=0,1-\alpha} = t_{df_j,1-\alpha/k}$, i.e. using the Bonferroni inequality. Thus also a solution for $N(\mu_j, \sigma_j^2)$ is easily possible by using Welch t-tests. For small n_j this test is conservative, since it does not use the common df , but df_j in each comparison.

20.4 Graphical display

The most widely used method in publications and reports is the asterisk representation of significances (dichotomized derived from the adjusted p-values) in tables and barcharts, followed by the letter-type display (e.g. available in library (multcompView) and the function `cld()` in library(multcomp) for all-pairs comparisons). Boxplots with plotted raw data allow an easy insight into the data conditions in addition to the foreground shift effects and their related adjusted p-values [101]. The most informative appears to be the side-by-side display of boxplots and the confidence interval plot for a suitably interpretable effect size.

20.5 Software

The following CRAN packages contain related functionality: *library(multcomp)*, *library(mratios)*, *library(emmeans)*, *library(mvtnorm)*, *library(MCPAN)*, *library(ETC)*, *library(MtO)*, *library(multtest)*, *library(gMCP)*, *library(mutoss)*, *library(nparcomp)*.

20.6 Appendix R Code and examples

See web-page: www.hothorn.de

Epilog

My habilitation thesis (a historically very German type of a second doctoral thesis) was motivated by the interplay between Williams/Dunnett tests and Harry Posten's lecture on the robustness of significance tests at the Schwerin conference of the same name in the eighties. I first met Charlie Dunnett at an International Conference on Simultaneous Inference at McMaster University in the early 1990s (on the occasion of his retirement) and later at the 1st MCP Conference in Tel Aviv (in the picture he is in the 2nd row, the 2nd from left).

Therefore, I have also a personal desire to write a summary essay for the Dunnett test - from my point of view as a special case of multiple contrast testing, especially the maxT test using the multiple marginal models approach. This overview has no claim to originality in all parts, only the versatility of the modifications for different real data scenarios and their software realization with CRAN packages is supposed to be shown. I use comprehensible R code not only as a case study, but also as a kind of formula-free representation of very complex statistical tests.

21 Final remark

This report will provide an overview on numerous modifications of the Dunnett test for many designs and data conditions- and has no claim to an original style of publication. It is a mix of well-known and new approaches, some taken directly from previous publications with my person (LAH) as author or co-author (see the reference list), especially R-code with data examples. Thereby some passages, code and data examples were taken over directly.

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